

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF CONTINUOUS PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIMENTAL WORK

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Abstract. *This article gives a general description of the organization of continuous pedagogical practice, trial work, the concept of systematization of continuous pedagogical practice, experimental application of the concept of systematization of continuous pedagogical practice to the training process of students of physical culture in higher educational institutions and a comprehensive study of the educational process and the initial state of continuous pedagogical practice and the determination of the level of professional and pedagogical training of students. Document analysis. To formulate a working hypothesis, set research objectives and solve them, traditional (qualitative) and formalized (qualitative-quantitative) methods of document research were used.*

Keywords: *pedagogical practice, formation, qualified, professional, training, development, research, methods.*

Introduction

The internship program used in our study shows the multi-functionality of the practitioner's activity, which confirms the need to properly train students to consciously apply professional-pedagogical and methodical knowledge in their practical work.

The successful realization of students' knowledge in the period of continuous pedagogical practice implies, firstly, remembering the previously acquired knowledge necessary to solve the practical problems, and secondly, combining them.

Analysis of the literature

Many authors write about this issue: Scientists who study the pedagogical process as a whole process in developing the methodological foundations of our scientific research work: K.A.Axmedov, V.P.Bespal'ko, M.A.Danilov, S.D.Dolimov, L.V.3ankov, A.3unnunov, D.Zohidova, I.Ya.Lerner, K.J.Mirsaidov, I.T.Ogorodnikov, N.S.Saydahmedov, U.Tolipov, Yo.Haydarov, R.K.CHoriev, P.Ishonov and others' scientific and methodological opinions took an important place. To solve the problems of development of professional skills and qualifications N.SH. Almetov, S.Ya. Batshev, A.P. Belyaeva, M.A. Zhidelyov, Z.K. Ismailova, K.N. Katkhanov, I.Ya. Lerner, N.A. Muslimov, K.J. Mirsaidov, A.M. Novikov, H.F. Rashidov, V.A. Skakun, O'.Q. Scientists such as Tolipov, D.A. Fayzullaeva, P.Z.Ishanov, O.F.Fyodorova, V.A.Chichkov, R.K.Choriev, SH.Kurbanov, SH.S.Sharipov, S.A.Shaporinsky made a great contribution.

According to the writings of T.S. Usmonkhudzhaev, P. Khojaev, L. TSetlina, I.A. Koshbakhtiev, M.B. Sapparbaev, A. Abdiev, J.E. Yusupov, such a structure of the system of training highly qualified specialists is not considered new, because in most countries professional higher education built on a multi-level basis. The analysis of educational experiences of the previous period proves that the conditions for the multi-level structure of the higher vocational school have already been created.

Research methodology

Starting from the 2022-2023 academic year, weekly training sessions for students of the 2nd-4th level studying full-time at the Tashkent State Pedagogical University will be held in the "4+2" format, including 4 days of classes at the higher education institution. On the 2nd day, it is planned to be conducted in general secondary education institutions in the order of practice.

Among the many issues that are important in solving the problem of professional training of students, the content of the educational process in continuous pedagogical practice is considered the most important. Organization of theoretical knowledge of professional and pedagogical training in practice is the basis of training of a physical education specialist.

This means that the process of professional training of specialists is built on the basis of the mechanism of mutual integration of theory and practice. That is, the acquisition of theoretical knowledge is inextricably linked with pedagogical practice. In this case, mastering the theory and mastering the pedagogical practice is considered a necessary condition, which in turn serves to consolidate the initial theoretical knowledge, and at the same time serves as a starting point for the further mastering of the pedagogical theory.

Analysis and results

Thus, by experiment we understand a planned and implemented pedagogical process, which includes new elements and allows to see the connection between differences more deeply than usual and to clearly consider the results of the introduced changes».

The essential characteristics of pedagogical experience are as follows:

- a) introduction of important changes in the pedagogical process in accordance with the task and hypothesis of the research;
- b) organization of a pedagogical process that allows to see the connection between the studied phenomena and their integral nature;
- c) in-depth qualitative analysis and as accurate as possible quantitative measurement of the new or modified components included in the pedagogical process and the results of the entire process.

The analysis of scientific-pedagogical literature indicates that there are general principles of organizing experimental work regardless of the content. In accordance with our research, we have taken the following principles as a basis:

- Experimental research should be based on a methodologically based hypothesis;
- The experiment must have a characteristic that ensures that the conclusions can be proven;
- Necessary loss of independent variables so that they do not affect dependent variables;
- The experiment should be built on an objective basis, that is, a scientific approach should be followed.

Our pedagogic experience consisted of the trial application of the concept of systematization of continuous pedagogic practice for the purpose of professional-pedagogical training of future teachers to the educational process of training physical education students of higher educational institutions.

Accordingly, the following issues of experience were defined:

- practical implementation of the concept of systematization of continuous pedagogical practice;
- checking the pedagogical conditions of the concept based on experience;

- testing the developed program of pedagogical practice on the basis of experience;
- determination of effectiveness of implementation of the concept of systematization of continuous pedagogical practice;
- presentation of experimental test results in quantitative and schematic-graphic form.

Experimental work was carried out in three stages.

At the first - initial stage - it was necessary to comprehensively study the current educational process in the higher educational institution and determine the initial state of continuous pedagogical practice and the level of professional and pedagogical training of students.

Preparation for experimental work consisted in solving the following issues:

- determination of problems and goals of experimental research;
- selection of experimental subject, object and theoretical justification of its implementation;
- express the hypothesis of the experiment;
- choosing the required number of experimental objects (the number of experimental and control groups, the number of students in them);
- determining the duration of the experiment;
- choosing specific methods for studying the initial state of the experimental object;
- determination of the signs that can reflect on the changes in the object of experience as a result of appropriate pedagogical influence.

The second stage consists of conducting a transformative (creative) experiment, during which a certain system of activities was tested:

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- carrying out experiments on identifying and checking the complex of pedagogical conditions;
- formation of efficiency criteria of experimental methodology for vocational and pedagogical training of students;
- recording information about the progress of the experiment based on the intermediate sections representing the changes under the influence of the experimental system of events;
- Show difficulties and possible shortcomings during the experiment;

The third stage — the control-corrective stage included the following:

- Analysis of received experimental data;
- Comparison of analytical materials with the purpose, objectives and hypothesis of the research;
- Regular processing of experimental results, drawing up graphs, tables, schemes;
- final diagnosis of the level of professional-pedagogical training of future specialists and professional skills of practicing Methodists;
- to describe the characteristics of subjects of experimental influence (students and methodologists);
- understanding and analytical presentation of materials and conclusions.

We took into account the requirement of representativeness during the research process.

Our research was conducted in higher education institutions. The number of students during the experiment was 375.

In addition, 25 practice managers participated in the experiment.

Pilot studies were conducted starting in 2020, and pilot studies were organized in 2021. In each stream, research was conducted throughout the educational period. Experimental work was organized in the bases of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, Andijan State University, Jizzakh Pedagogical Institute.

Various empirical research methods were used during the experimental work. Their application was directed to obtaining methodological, theoretical and didactic conclusions.

The following methods were used in experimental work to determine independent and dependent variables:

- survey-diagnostics (questionnaires, interviews, tests, "rating" assessment, summarization of independent indicators);
- observational (direct, indirect, included observation, record of trainings and activities);
- praxeometric (analysis of curricula and regulatory documents, practice programs, analysis of the results of professional and pedagogical activities of students and Methodists);
- experimental (recording, formative and diagnostic pedagogical experience);
- mathematical statistics methods.

We will consider some methods of experimental research.

Observation in pedagogy is a long-term, goal-oriented and systematic method of perception of events and processes based on perception.

In our experience, the main task of observation was to describe in detail the process of organizing a continuous pedagogical practice, analyzing it and determining the cause-and-effect relationships between the obtained results, the content of the programs and the conditions of implementation.

The observation made it possible to carry out a number of other tasks, which include: the process of mastering the necessary educational materials, the effectiveness of acquiring the necessary educational methods and tools and the methodology of conducting educational work, difficulties in the process of adapting to the conditions of the educational institution. the process, their consistent use of methodological methods; to analyze the changes in the characteristics of pedagogical activities in the process of conducting a specific lesson or educational event.

To address these issues, we initially developed a monitoring program that considered the following situations:

- the purpose of observation;
- the conditions under which it is conducted;
- object of observation; subject;
- observation time and analysis of obtained results.

Experimental work was carried out throughout the academic year in general schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges.

As an example, we present the program for monitoring the activities of students-practitioners in the physical education class during the internship period in the second year of the general education school.

- general information: date, school, practitioner's last name, name, training topic.
- Determination of the didactic goals of the lesson by the student.
- At a specific stage of the lesson and in the course of the nose training session.
- the correct selection of methods and tools of educational activity.
- The level of knowledge of important concepts, skills and abilities on the subject.

- Evaluation of the development of a system of tasks and exercises for students.
- The structure and organization of trainings: starting on time, active participation in trainings, the final part. Preparation of training places and equipment.
- Goal-oriented, scientific, appropriate for educational tasks.
- Collective, group and individual work; level of interest of students.
- Analysis of lesson results and overall assessment.

The next method used during experimental work is interview.

The main feature of the considered method, unlike other methods of information gathering, is that the interaction between the researcher and the subject affects the results of the research. In addition, the researcher influences the interview process and directs the interlocutor in the right direction.

For this reason, we paid special attention to the mutual relations of the two parties when using the method.

The quality of the information obtained as a result of the interview depends on its proper organization and thorough preparation. Reliability and accuracy are criteria of information quality. For this reason, we took a special approach to creating an interview plan, asking questions and justifying them. We divide the planning and conduct of the interview into three stages: adaptation, achieving the set goal and de-escalation.

Different categories of people participated in the interview:

- 1) practicing students;
- 2) practice leaders;
- 3) students:

In cases where the participants of such a conversation are sharply different in age and other characteristics, separate appropriate relations are required.

The participation of a wide range of people in the interview made it possible to get full information about the effectiveness of the continuous pedagogical practice model, about various situations and events of the practice process, about the motivations, interests and needs of students, and to observe their adaptation to the conditions of the educational institution.

Thus, the characteristics of the organization of the practice process were determined from three points of view:

- from the first side — pedagogues;
- on the other hand — students;
- on the third side — the students-practitioners themselves.

This made it possible to better analyze the process of studying and learning.

Questionnaire is a questionnaire that is filled out independently by the participants of the survey according to the rules specified in it. Questionnaire questions should be expressed in very clear, unambiguous, understandable language for survey participants.

Examining the answers to the questions is related to the main topics and sections of the continuous pedagogical practice program, the development of pedagogical skills and abilities of student-practitioners, adaptation to the conditions of the educational institution, professional responsibility and activity. allows to determine other issues.

We created the questionnaire separately for practitioners of each course. We tried to reflect in them which sections of the experimental program aroused their interest and why, which types

of education and training activities interested them more, what difficulties they felt in learning the educational material, and what they were not satisfied with in the process of practical activity. .

We compared and summarized the data from questionnaires with other methods - document analysis, direct observation, interviews.

"Rating" assessment. To determine the manifestation of professional-pedagogical skills in students and methodologists, the method of assessment, or otherwise, the method of expert assessment, was used.

Conclusion/Recommendations.

Document analysis. Traditional (qualitative) and formalized (qualitative-quantitative) methods of studying documents were used to formulate a working hypothesis, set research tasks and solve them. Using these methods, the following documents were studied:

- Legal documents for ensuring the development of physical education and sports adopted in our country;
- State educational standards;
- physical training curricula and programs of higher educational institutions;
- professional qualification characteristics, professional programs and requirements for professional training of a specialist;
- related to practice preparation, organization, conduct and control;
- documents of students and Methodists on practice (diaries, reports, etc.).

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